

**ILMIY VA
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**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 3 (Май-Июнь)

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ОРТОКЕРАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЛИНЗ НА АККОМОДАЦИЮ ПРИ МИОПИИ СЛАБОЙ И СРЕДНЕЙ СТЕПЕНИ У ДЕТЕЙ

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Аннотация. Миопия широко распространена среди детей школьного возраста и характеризуется тенденцией к прогрессированию, что может приводить к снижению зрительных функций и развитию осложнений. В связи с этим, особую актуальность приобретают методы коррекции, способные не только обеспечивать высокое качество зрения, но и оказывать влияние на механизмы, участвующие в прогрессировании миопии. Одним из таких методов является ортокератология, основанная на использовании ночных жестких газопроницаемых линз для временного изменения формы роговицы. Цель исследования – оценить влияние ортокератологических линз на состояние аккомодационного аппарата у детей с миопией слабой и средней степени. **Материалы и методы:** Всем пациентам проводилось комплексное офтальмологическое обследование детей с миопией слабой и средней степени, включавшее визометрию, авторефрактометрию, скиаскопию в условиях циклоплегии, биометрию, биомикроскопию и офтальмоскопию. Для оценки аккомодационной функции определяли объём абсолютной аккомодации (ОАА), запас относительной аккомодации (ЗОА). Объём абсолютной аккомодации исследовали с использованием аппарата АКА-0.1, а запас относительной аккомодации определяли по методике Аветисова – Шаповалова. Исследования проводились до подбора ортокератологических линз и в различные сроки их применения. Полученные данные использовались для оценки влияния ортокератологической коррекции на состояние аккомодационного аппарата и динамику функциональных показателей у детей с миопией слабой и средней

степени. **Результаты:** использование ортокератологических линз у детей с миопией слабой и средней степени способствует улучшению показателей аккомодации, повышению остроты зрения без коррекции и стабилизации рефракционных показателей. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о положительном влиянии ортокератологической коррекции на аккомодационную функцию у детей с миопией. **Заключение:** Результаты проведенного исследования показали, что использование ортокератологических линз в ночном режиме у детей с миопией слабой и средней степени оказывает благоприятное воздействие на аккомодационный аппарат глаза. В ходе наблюдения отмечено увеличение показателей объема абсолютной аккомодации и запаса относительной аккомодации, что свидетельствует об улучшении функциональной активности аккомодационной системы. Наряду с этим, наблюдалось повышение остроты зрения без дополнительной коррекции и положительная динамика рефракционных показателей. Полученные данные подтверждают эффективность ортокератологической коррекции как метода, способствующего не только улучшению зрительных функций, но и оптимизации аккомодационных механизмов, имеющих важное значение в контроле прогрессирования миопии у детей.

Ключевые слова: миопия, дети, ортокератологическая коррекция, ортокератологические линзы, близорукость, аккомодационная функция, объем абсолютной аккомодации, запас относительной аккомодации, аккомодация, подростки, прогрессирование миопии, контроль миопии.

INFLUENCE OF ORTHOKERATOLOGY LENSES ON ACCOMMODATION IN CHILDREN WITH LOW AND MODERATE MYOPIA

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Abstract. Myopia is widespread among school-aged children and is characterized by a tendency to progress, which may lead to decreased visual functions and the development of complications. In this regard, methods of correction that can not only provide high-quality vision but also influence the mechanisms involved in myopia progression are of particular relevance. One such method is orthokeratology, based on the use of overnight rigid gas-permeable lenses for temporary reshaping of the cornea. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of orthokeratology lenses on the condition of the accommodative apparatus in children with low and moderate myopia. **Materials and methods:** All patients underwent a comprehensive ophthalmological examination of children with low and moderate myopia, including visometry, autorefractometry, skiascopy under cycloplegia, biometry, biomicroscopy, and ophthalmoscopy. To assess accommodative function, the amplitude of absolute accommodation (AAA) and the reserve of relative accommodation (RRA) were determined. The amplitude of absolute accommodation was examined using the AKA-0.1 device, while the reserve of relative accommodation was determined according to the Avetisov–Shapovalov method. Examinations were carried out before orthokeratology lens fitting and at various periods of their use. The obtained data were used to evaluate the effect of orthokeratology correction on the condition of the accommodative apparatus and the dynamics of functional parameters in children with low and moderate myopia. **Results:** The use of orthokeratology lenses in children with low and moderate myopia contributes to improved accommodation parameters, increased uncorrected visual acuity, and stabilization of refractive parameters. The obtained results indicate a positive effect of orthokeratology correction on accommodative function in children with myopia. **Conclusion:** The results of the study demonstrated that the use of overnight orthokeratology lenses in children with low and moderate myopia has a

beneficial effect on the accommodative apparatus of the eye. During the observation period, an increase in the amplitude of absolute accommodation and the reserve of relative accommodation was noted, indicating improved functional activity of the accommodative system. In addition, an increase in uncorrected visual acuity and positive dynamics of refractive parameters were observed. The obtained data confirm the effectiveness of orthokeratology correction as a method that contributes not only to the improvement of visual functions but also to the optimization of accommodative mechanisms, which are of great importance in controlling myopia progression in children.

Keywords: myopia, children, orthokeratology correction, orthokeratology lenses, nearsightedness, accommodative function, amplitude of absolute accommodation, reserve of relative accommodation, accommodation, adolescents, myopia progression, myopia control.

Introduction. Myopia is one of the most common refractive anomalies in children and adolescents and represents a serious medical and social problem in modern ophthalmology. According to the World Health Organization, the prevalence of myopia worldwide continues to increase steadily, and its progression in childhood is associated with an increased risk of pathological fundus changes, elongation of the axial length of the eye, and deterioration of visual functions. In this regard, studies aimed at investigating the mechanisms of myopia development and developing effective methods for its control are of particular importance [1].

At present, it has been proven that the condition of the accommodative apparatus of the eye plays an important role in the development and progression of myopia. Studies have shown that reduced accommodative ability, insufficiency of accommodative response, decreased amplitude of absolute accommodation, and reduced reserves of relative accommodation may contribute to the progression of the myopic process in children. Authors emphasize the necessity of timely diagnosis and

correction of accommodative disorders as one of the directions for preventing myopia progression [2].

A significant contribution to the study of the relationship between accommodation and myopia has been made by domestic and foreign researchers. Their studies have shown that children with myopia, especially those with progressive myopia, often demonstrate accommodative dysfunction, including insufficiency of accommodative response and reduced functional reserves of the accommodative apparatus. It has also been established that children with myopia exhibit an insufficient accommodative response to visual defocus compared with children without myopia, indicating specific features of accommodative system functioning in this refractive pathology. These findings emphasize the importance of assessing accommodation and its correction when selecting methods for controlling myopia progression [3,4].

Of particular interest are studies devoted to the investigation of accommodative function during orthokeratology correction. Authors have found that the use of orthokeratology lenses contributes to a reduction in accommodative response lag, increases the accuracy of accommodative response, improves accommodative sensitivity, and enhances the functional reserves of the accommodative apparatus. These changes may provide an additional positive effect on the course of the myopic process and the effectiveness of its control [5].

Studies conducted in the Central Asian region indicate that the use of modern methods of myopia correction, including orthokeratology, contributes to slowing myopia progression in children and has a positive effect on the clinical and functional parameters of the visual system, confirming the effectiveness of this method of myopia control and its influence on the functional condition of the accommodative apparatus [6].

In addition, numerous studies confirm the effectiveness of orthokeratology lenses in controlling myopia progression and indicate their influence on the

functional condition of the visual system, including accommodative parameters. At the same time, despite the considerable number of publications on this issue, certain parameters of accommodative function, such as the amplitude of absolute accommodation and the reserve of relative accommodation in children with low and moderate myopia, remain insufficiently studied, which necessitates further research in this area [7].

Thus, studying the effect of orthokeratology lenses on the accommodative apparatus in children with low and moderate myopia remains an important scientific and practical task aimed at improving methods for controlling myopia progression and increasing the effectiveness of its correction.

Materials and methods. The study included 80 patients (160 eyes) with myopia of varying severity. Among them, 30 patients (60 eyes) were diagnosed with low myopia, and 50 patients (100 eyes) with moderate myopia. The mean age of the examined patients was 12.0 ± 0.38 years.

The control group consisted of 20 children (40 eyes) with a similar refractive pathology: 10 patients (20 eyes) had low myopia and 10 patients (20 eyes) had moderate myopia. The age of the participants in the control group ranged from 8 to 15 years, with a mean age of 11.57 ± 1.4 years. Correction in this group was performed using monofocal spectacles worn continuously.

The mean values of the spherical equivalent of refraction were $(-2.2 \pm 0.25$ D in low myopia and $(-4.7 \pm 0.22$ D in moderate myopia. Corneal astigmatism was within 0.75 ± 0.22 D and 0.92 ± 0.54 D, respectively.

All patients underwent a comprehensive ophthalmological examination, including visometry, autorefractometry (Grand Seiko YR-2100), ophthalmometry (Topcon KR-7300), biometry (Zeiss IOL Master 500), corneal topography (SW-600 corneal topography system), and cycloplegic skiascopy. Additional examinations included biomicroscopy using an L-0240 slit lamp, binocular ophthalmoscopy according to Schepens using a VOLK 90D lens, assessment of the amplitude of

absolute accommodation (AAA) with the AKA-0.1 device, and determination of the reserve of relative accommodation (RRA) according to the Avetisov–Shapovalov method. Follow-up assessments were performed at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. Ocular hydrodynamics according to Nesterov was also evaluated. All examinations were performed before the initiation of orthokeratology lens wear and during the follow-up period.

Reverse geometry orthokeratology lenses “Moonlens” (Sky Optix company) were fitted individually for each patient. No complications associated with lens wear were detected during the observation period.

Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using standard methods of variation statistics with Microsoft Office 2010 (Windows XP) and Statistica software. Results are presented as mean value and standard deviation ($M \pm m$). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. During the observation of children with low and moderate myopia using orthokeratology lenses, a pronounced positive dynamics of the main functional parameters of the visual system was established. Already in the early follow-up periods (1–3 months), a significant increase in uncorrected visual acuity was observed, reaching 1.0 ± 0.02 in low myopia and 0.9 ± 0.028 in moderate myopia, while maintaining stable values throughout the observation period (6–12 months), which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Against the background of orthokeratology correction, a pronounced reduction in the degree of myopia was revealed. Thus, in low myopia, the spherical equivalent decreased from $(-2.2 \pm 0.25$ D to $(-0.46 \pm 0.15$ D, and in moderate myopia from $(-4.7 \pm 0.22$ D to $(-1.0 \pm 0.2$ D, confirming the effectiveness of this method in correcting refractive disorders ($p < 0.01$).

Particular attention in the study was paid to assessing the condition of the accommodative apparatus. It was established that the use of orthokeratology lenses was accompanied by a marked improvement in accommodative function. A

significant increase in the amplitude of absolute accommodation (AAA) was observed, rising from 5.2 ± 0.07 D to 7.6 ± 0.23 D in patients with low myopia and from 5.8 ± 0.14 D to 8.5 ± 0.01 D in moderate myopia ($p < 0.05$).

A similar positive dynamics was identified for the reserve of relative accommodation (RRA), which increased almost 1.5-fold. In children with low myopia, values increased from 3.3 ± 0.36 D to 5.2 ± 0.14 D, and in moderate myopia from 2.85 ± 0.23 D to 5.0 ± 0.2 D ($p < 0.01$). These findings indicate an improvement in the functional reserves of the accommodative apparatus during orthokeratology correction.

When comparing the results with the control group using monofocal spectacle correction, it was found that the positive dynamics of accommodative parameters was more pronounced in the patients of the main group. Thus, the amplitude of absolute accommodation in children of the control group with low myopia increased from 5.3 ± 0.09 D to 5.9 ± 0.18 D, and in moderate myopia from 5.7 ± 0.12 D to 6.1 ± 0.21 D. At the same time, in the orthokeratology correction group, this parameter reached 7.6 ± 0.23 D and 8.5 ± 0.01 D, respectively ($p < 0.05$). A similar trend was observed when assessing the reserve of relative accommodation. In the control group, values increased from 3.2 ± 0.28 D to 4.0 ± 0.16 D in low myopia and from 2.8 ± 0.24 D to 3.9 ± 0.19 D in moderate myopia. In the main group, the increase was more pronounced, reaching 5.2 ± 0.14 D and 5.0 ± 0.2 D, respectively ($p < 0.01$). The most significant differences between the groups were observed after 6 and 12 months of follow-up. The obtained results indicate a more pronounced positive effect of orthokeratology correction on the functional condition of the accommodative apparatus compared with traditional spectacle correction.

The obtained data indicate that the identified changes demonstrate not only the optical effect of orthokeratology lenses but also their significant influence on the functional condition of the accommodative system in children with low and moderate myopia.

The results of the study allow us to conclude that orthokeratology correction in children with low and moderate myopia has a complex positive effect on the visual system. In addition to a pronounced improvement in uncorrected visual acuity and a reduction in the degree of myopia, a statistically significant improvement in the functional condition of the accommodative apparatus was observed, manifested by an increase in the amplitude of absolute accommodation and the reserve of relative accommodation.

Thus, orthokeratology lenses can be considered not only as an effective method of optical correction of myopia but also as a means of functional influence on the accommodative system, which is of great importance for the stabilization and control of the myopic process in children.

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